

Determination of lead content in the most popular brands of lipsticks in Sulaimani, Iraq

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Abstract : Recent reports describing the presence of lead (Pb) in lipsticks have suggested that, under ordinary use, the potential amount of Pb exposure is harmful. This study aims to investigate the content of lead in most frequently used brands of solid lipstick in Sulaimani, Iraq. 30 solid lipstick samples (5 colors from 6 different brands) were selected taken from large cosmetic stores in Sulaimani (Iraq) and lead of them was analyzed by flame atomic absorption spectrometer (AAAnalyst 700) with detection limit of 0.05 ppm. The results showed that the concentration of lead in the lipsticks was within the range of 0.45–48.59 µg/g. There was significant difference between the averages of the lead content in the different brands of the lipsticks. Thus, the continuous use of these cosmetics can increase the absorption of heavy metals, especially Pb, in the body when swallowing lipsticks or through dermal cosmetic absorption. The effects of heavy metals such as lead can be harmful, especially for pregnant women and children. Therefore, effort must be made to inform the users and the general public about the harmful consequences of cosmetics.

Keywords : Cosmetic, lipstick samples, lead, Atomic Absorption Spectrometer, Sulaimani.

Introduction

Since the beginning of civilization, cosmetics have constituted a part of routine body care not only by the upper strata of society but also by middle and low class people. Although beauty consciousness of people has set the demand of cosmetics in market, the side effects as well as health consciousness of people has attracted the clinicians and researchers to find out the probable reason behind their side effects. Heavy metal contamination is one of the important reasons behind the same problem. Heavy metals like lead are common contaminant in various cosmetic products^{1,2}. The US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) issued warnings in 2003 for litargirio, a yellow- or peach-colored powder used in traditional remedies by people of Central America and the Caribbean region, particularly the Dominican Republic, because it contains up to 79% Pb. Also, in 2003 and 2006 the FDA issued warnings for kohl, a traditional cosmetic eyeliner common in the Middle East, North Africa, Sub-Saharan Africa, and South Asia, because it frequently contains more than 50% Pb. Recent media reports and e-mail hoaxes describing the presence of Pb in lipsticks

have suggested that under conditions of ordinary use, the potential amount of Pb exposure is harmful³⁻⁵. Al-Saleh *et al.* showed that heavy metals (e.g. lead) can be absorbed by children's and women's skin through using cosmetic products^{6,7}. Lipsticks may be contaminated with Pb if they are manufactured with ingredients that naturally contain Pb or are produced under conditions that could introduce Pb into the ingredients in lipsticks¹⁵. It has been determined that women unintentionally swallow 4 pounds of lipstick during their life¹⁴. The long term usage of this product may have negative effect on women's health. Therefore, precaution needs to be taken accordingly. The use of leaded cosmetics such as lipstick has been found to severely affect human beings, especially pregnant women, young children, and fetus. In pregnant women lead can easily cross the placenta and produce congenital lead poisoning^{20,22}. Contact with low concentration of lead can cause disorders such as behavioral abnormalities and decreased learning and hearing and can result in adverse effects on central nervous system, reproductive system, hematopoiesis, anemia, and hepatic and renal systems⁸⁻¹¹. More than 90% of lead absorbed

by human is concentrated in the bones with a half-life of greater than 20 years¹². In 2007, a study on the lead concentration of 33 brands of lipsticks showed that 61% of tested lipsticks have measurable lead (0.03–0.65 $\mu\text{g/g}$)³. In 2009, a research was done by Nancy M. Hepp *et al.* to determine total lead in 20 lipsticks under ten brand names, using the inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). All of the lipsticks contained detectable amounts of Pb, with values ranging from 0.09 to 3.06 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and an average amount of 1.07 $\mu\text{g/g}$ ¹⁵. In 2011 the Joint Research Centre, a Directorate General of the European Commission, carried out a monitoring study on a reasonably large number of commercially available lipsticks¹⁶, using ICP-MS. The concentration of total lead in the lipsticks analyzed varied from below 1 $\mu\text{g/g}$ up to 3.75 $\mu\text{g/g}$. Also, FDA has shown that the average concentration of lead in 400 samples of lipsticks was 1.11 $\mu\text{g/g}$ ¹⁷. So far, FDA has not set specific admissible Pb content in cosmetics. However, dyes and pigments used as ingredients in lipsticks are regulated as color additives by the FDA and must undergo premarket approval by the agency before they may be used in any cosmetics. The FDA controls potential Pb exposure from color additives by setting admissible limit of 20 $\mu\text{g Pb/g}$ (20 ppm)¹³.

Material and methods :

Sample collection :

30 solid lipstick samples (5 colors in 6 brands) were selected in large cosmetic stores in Sulaimani (Iraq) in order to having a homogeneous sample from each specific color and brand and to increase the results reliability, 3 random pieces of each sample were taken and blended so that the final sample was a mixture of 3 same weighted pieces of same color and brand lipstick. The colors studied for each brand of lipstick were peach puff, violet, deep pink, chocolate, and red.

Sample preparation and analysis :

Lipsticks are present in the semi-solid form, so these required pretreatment before analysis. Lipsticks are organic in nature. For this purpose 1 g of lipstick samples were exactly weighted with electrical analytical balance, the same 3 products were mixed properly, 1 g of that was put into the 50 mL pyrex glass beaker. Sample preparation for heavy metal analysis was done under standard procedure. Briefly, 1 g of each sample was digested in approximately 5 ml mixture of concentrated acid (nitric and perchloric acids (Merck 99.99%) in 3 : 1 ratio) for 2–3 h on a hot plate. If black or brown color is appeared, then again add 3.0 ml of mixture of concentrated acids to find out the white colored sample. The above digested samples were dissolved in nitric acid 0.1 M and filtered with the help of Whatman number 1 filter paper. The clear solution was used for metal quantification. Samples were stored in clean labeled sample bottles until analysis. The lead content of lipstick samples was measured by Flame Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer, Model : A Analyst 700). All results are expressed in $\mu\text{g/g}$ on the basis of wet weight.

Experimental Results

30 samples of lipsticks were investigated in this study. The samples analyzed showed that lead was detected in all brands of the cosmetics with varying concentrations (Table 1). As seen, the concentration of lead in the lipsticks was within the range of 0.45–48.59 $\mu\text{g/g}$ on the basis of wet weight. Based on the results illustrated in Table 1, there are significant differences between the lead content in the different brands (Fig. 1) and different colors (Fig. 2) of the lipsticks. It can be said that generally darker colors have more lead content rather than brighter colors and in most of the cases the red lipsticks contains highest lead concentration. A logical trend in lead concentration based on the color can be seen so that all the

Table 1. Concentration ($\mu\text{g/g}$ on the basis of wet weight) of lead in different brands

Brand/Color	A	B	C	D	E	F
Peach puff	6.92 \pm 0.184	0.68 \pm 0.074	0.95 \pm 0.054	0.60 \pm 0.093	3.54 \pm 0.048	0.45 \pm 0.059
Violet	5.36 \pm 0.114	1.13 \pm 0.057	1.34 \pm 0.032	2.25 \pm 0.006	6.08 \pm 0.056	0.67 \pm 0.105
Deep pink	11.1 \pm 0.056	1.04 \pm 0.141	2.51 \pm 0.137	3.23 \pm 0.122	9.56 \pm 0.107	0.95 \pm 0.054
Chocolate	9.49 \pm 0.083	2.69 \pm 0.045	1.85 \pm 0.076	4.42 \pm 0.056	12.49 \pm 0.112	1.30 \pm 0.171
Red	12.09 \pm 0.039	3.15 \pm 0.076	3.87 \pm 0.155	6.34 \pm 0.093	48.59 \pm 0.049	1.28 \pm 0.037

Fig. 1. The mean content of lead ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in each color of overall lipsticks regardless of its brand.

Fig. 2. The mean content of lead ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in each brand (showed as A-F) regardless of its color.

Fig. 3. The content of lead ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in lipsticks from six different brands (showed as A-F) on their color basis. The lead content of red color lipstick in brand E ($48.56 \mu\text{g/g}$) has not been plotted on the chart.

measurements can be categorized in the following order of Red > Chocolate > Deep pink > Violet > Peach

Fig. 4. The general trend in lead concentration based on lipstick colors.

puff (Figs. 1 and 4). Almost in all of the products, the lead content was lower than 20 mg/kg. It has to be noted that there was not a logical relationship between the distributions of lead content and lipstick prices; however, the highest concentration of lead was detected in a red color cheap Chinese lipstick. The result of comparing overall lipstick's lead content based on their colors under different brands has depicted in Fig. 3, also the general trend in lead concentration based on lipstick colors is shown in Fig. 4.

Discussion

In comparison with other sources such as water, air, and food, daily exposure to heavy metals from cosmetics has been considered as a negligible source for human. Nevertheless, because of the cumulative properties of heavy metals in the body during life time, cosmetics can be regarded as a substantial source of the metals^{20,21}. Even under the best producing methods in the factories, the existence of heavy metals in cosmetics is inevitable²⁰. Therefore, in order to diminish the adverse health effects of heavy metals, cosmetics producers must use such ingredients as color additives in their cosmetics to meet FDA's requirements.

Many studies have proven the relation between consuming leaded cosmetics (lipstick and eye shadow) and elevated blood lead levels^{2,23}. Blood lead levels under $10 \mu\text{g/dL}$ may damage neurobehavioral development in children. It has been proved that by increasing one microgram lead per deciliter ($\mu\text{g Pb/dL}$) of blood, the intelligence quotient (IQ) of children is reduced by 0.25 points²⁴. Lead has also been related to infertility and miscarriage².

The continuous use of cosmetics could have adverse effects on the ocular system²⁰. These harmful effects can be caused by skin contact²⁵.

As it was aforementioned above, FDA has not set specific admissible Pb content in cosmetics, except that color additives permitted as ingredients are usually limited to 20 µg Pb/g (20 ppm). Using this value it was concluded that except in one sample (cheap red lipstick from China) in all brands and colors the lead concentration was below the FDA limit. Also, the campaign for safe cosmetics has given the 0.1 ppm admissible lead level in candy. Given this, in all brands lead level was higher than CSC (Campaign for Safe Cosmetics) safe limit value but it should be considered that a portion of lipstick which is swallowed is notably less than amount of candy.

In our study it has been seen that generally, darker colors regardless of brand's type contain more lead concentration. Therefore, we suggest authorities to monitoring safety checks on cosmetic products before importing to other countries such as Kurdistan.

Conclusion

In conclusion, although the lead content in lipsticks might not cause an immediate health problem; its accumulative effects due to repeated application cannot be ignored and will cause serious problems in long term usage. Hence, it seems important to halt importing unsafe cosmetics. Establishing a safety assessment committee from health authorities to control the quality of products in a regular basis would be a good alternative at the meanwhile.

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